

GNU Octave tools for GWAS

2022

Summary Statistics

The Example of The UK Biobank

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1 Introduction

The UK Biobank is a large-scale biomedical database that includes genetic data on 500,000 UK citizens ([Sudlow, C et al. 2015](#)). Myalgic Encephalomyelitis/Chronic Fatigue Syndrome (ME/CFS) is among the phenotypes reported by participants. The total number of ME/CFS patients included is 1208 females and 451 males, with control groups of more than 150 k individuals each. For each individual, 805,426 variants (both SNPs and short InDels) were genotyped. From them, up to 30 million variants can be imputed using haplotype maps. This is the biggest GWAS study on ME/CFS patients ever made, so far. Many research groups have analyzed this huge quantity of data and the conclusion, according to ([Dibble J. et al. 2020](#)), is that the only variants to be significantly different between patients and controls are included in gene [SLC25A15](#), which encodes mitochondrial ornithine transporter I, particularly variant rs7337312 (position13:41353297:G:A on reference genome GRCh37, forward strand). But this difference is statistically significant only when we consider female patients vs female controls. For a detailed discussion of this result, the best reference is the already mentioned ([Dibble J. et al. 2020](#)).

All the scripts presented in this document are written in [GNU Octave](#), version 6.3.0.

2 Input files and where to download them

The collection of the analysis generated by Neale's Lab with the UK Biobank data is available [here](#). In line 2 of that file, you can download an explanation of the labels ([README](#)). At lines 8, 9, 10 you can download a collection of the phenotypes and some of the attributes of the relative sample, for both sexes, females, and males respectively ([phenotypes.both_sexes.tsv](#), [phenotypes.female.tsv](#), [phenotypes.male.tsv](#)). We are interested in phenotype 20002_1482 (Non-cancer illness code, self-reported: chronic fatigue syndrome). In line 11 you find a file that contains the details on each variant ([variants.tsv](#)). These files must be unzipped before reading them. I placed the unzipped input files in the folder Genetics\Neale's Lab Metadata, while all the zipped files are in the folder Genetics\Neale's Lab Meta data\Original zipped files.

	A	B	C	...
A1	variant	Chr	pos	...
A2	1:15791:C:T	1	15791	...
:	:	:	:	:
A13364304	22:51237712:G:A	22	51237712	...
A13364305	X:2699555:C:A	X	2699555	...
:	:	:	:	:
A13791470	X:154930487:T:A	X	154930487	...

Table 1. Structure of the first three columns of variants.tsv. This file includes a total of 213 columns and of 13,791,470 lines.

2.1 File variants.tsv

File variants.tsv has 13,791,468 lines and 25 columns. It can't be opened by using Excel. My advice is to use EmEditor (both the professional version and the free version will do for just reading the content). The number of lines of variants.tsv is the number of variants included in the analysis, plus one (because one line goes for the labels). It includes 13,364,303 variants for autosomes. From line

A13364305 to line A13791470 we have further 427,166 variants on chromosome X; no variants on chromosome Y are included in this analysis (see Table 1).

variant	Variant identifier in the form "chr:pos:ref:alt", where "ref" is aligned to the forward strand.
chr	Chromosome of the variant.
pos	Position of the variant in GRCh37 coordinates.
ref	Reference allele on the forward strand.
alt	Alternate allele (not necessarily minor allele).
rsid	rsid (not guaranteed to be unique).
varid	Unique variant identifier included in imputed BGEN files.
consequence	Consequence annotated using VEP version 85.
consequence_category	Category of VEP-annotated consequence ("ptv", "missense", "synonymous", "non_coding").
info	Imputation INFO score as provided by UK Biobank.
call_rate	Call rate (calculated using hardcall ¹ genotypes).
AC	Alt allele count (calculated using hardcall genotypes).
AF	Alt ² allele frequency (calculated using hardcall genotypes).
minor_allele	Minor allele (equal to ref allele when AF > 0.5, otherwise equal to alt allele).
minor_AF	Minor allele frequency calculated using hardcall genotypes on n_called.
p_hwe	Hardy-Weinberg p-value.
n_called	Number of samples with defined genotype at this variant.
n_not_called	Number of samples without a defined genotype at this variant.
n_hom_ref	Number of samples with homozygous reference genotype at this variant.
n_het	Number of samples with heterozygous genotype at this variant.
n_hom_var	Number of samples with homozygous alternate genotype at this variant.
n_non_ref	Number of samples with non-homozygous reference genotype at this variant (n_het + n_hom_var)
r_heterozygosity	Proportion of samples with heterozygous genotype at this variant.
r_het_hom_var	Ratio of samples with heterozygous genotype to samples with homozygous alternate genotype at this variant.
r_expected_het_frequency	Expected r_heterozygosity based on Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium.

Table 2. Labels of each column of variants.tsv, and their meanings.

¹ Hardcall genotype values means: 0/1/2 for hom_Ref/het/hom_Var ([R](#)).

² The fact that AC and AF both refer to the alternate allele is indicated in the FAQ page of Neale Lab ([R](#)).

2.1.1 Variants annotation

The explanation for the meaning of the label of each column is included in the already mentioned README file, but I have collected them in Table 2 with only minor changes, to enhance clarity. Each variant has its VEP-annotated consequence and the various consequences have been collected under four big categories, according to the scheme in Table 3.

impact	consequence	consequence category	number of variants		
			1-22	X	tot
MODERATE	inframe_deletion	missense	192,317	3,044	195,361
MODERATE	inframe_insertion				
MODERATE	missense_variant				
MODERATE	protein_altering_variant				
LOW	splice_region_variant				
HIGH	start_lost				
HIGH	stop_lost				
HIGH	frameshift_variant	ptv	9,669	115	9,784
HIGH	splice_acceptor_variant				
HIGH	splice_donor_variant				
HIGH	stop_gained				
LOW	incomplete_terminal_codon_variant	synonymous	106,892	1,877	108,769
LOW	stop_retained_variant				
LOW	synonymous_variant				
MODIFIER	upstream_gene_variant	non_coding	13,055,425	422,128	13,477,553
MODIFIER	intron_variant				
MODIFIER	non_coding_transcript_exon_variant				
MODIFIER	downstream_gene_variant				
MODIFIER	intergenic_variant				
MODIFIER	3_prime_UTR_variant				
MODIFIER	5_prime_UTR_variant				
MODIFIER	regulatory_region_variant				
MODIFIER	TF_binding_site_variant				
MODIFIER	mature_miRNA_variant				
MODIFIER	TFBS_ablation				
MODIFIER	coding_sequence_variant				
MODIFIER	non_coding_transcript_variant				

Table 3. Each variant has its VEP-annotated consequence and the various consequences have been collected under four big categories, according to the scheme in this table. I have also indicated the total number of variants for each consequence category, their number within the autosomes (1-22), and how many of them fall in the X chromosome.

I have built this table by direct inspection of variants.tsv: by using EmEditor I have selected all the lines corresponding to the value missense in column consequence_category, then I have copied all column consequence in another file and I have eliminated duplicated lines. This gives a list of the consequences for missense. I have then repeated the same algorithm for the remaining three consequence categories. For a description of the meaning of the labels in the central column of the table, please visit [this page](#) on Ensemble’s website. The left column is taken from the mentioned page and the meaning of the attributes is as follows:

1. HIGH: the variant is assumed to have a high (disruptive) impact on the protein, probably causing protein truncation, loss of function, or triggering nonsense-mediated decay;
2. MODERATE: a non-disruptive variant that might change protein effectiveness;
3. LOW: assumed to be mostly harmless or unlikely to change protein behavior;
4. MODIFIER: usually non-coding variants or variants affecting non-coding genes, where predictions are difficult or there is no evidence of impact.

2.1.2 Alternative allele, reference allele, and minor allele

As a further note, AC and AF are the alternative allele count and frequency, respectively, among the sample n_called which is a total of 361,194 individuals. The count is made by a method called hardcall: at a given variant, we had 2 to AC if we have an individual who is homozygous for the alternative allele (hom_Var), we had 1 if the individual is heterozygous (het), we had zero in case of homozygosity for the reference allele (hom_Var) (R). Then we calculate:

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad \text{AF} = \frac{\text{AC}}{\text{n_called}} = \frac{\text{AC}}{361194}$$

Note that AF is the alternative allele frequency. When $\text{AF} > 0.5$, it is also the frequency of the major allele, and in this case $\text{minor_AF} = 1.0 - \text{AF}$ (Table 4).

CASES	Alternative allele frequency	Major allele frequency	Minor allele frequency	
$\text{AF} > 0.5$	AF	AF	$\text{minor_AF} = 1.0 - \text{AF}$	alternative allele = major allele reference allele = minor allele
$\text{AF} < 0.5$	AF	-	AF	alternative allele = minor allele reference allele = major allele

Table 4. AF is the alternative allele frequency. When $\text{AF} > 0.5$, it is also the frequency of the major allele and in this case $\text{minor_AF} = 1.0 - \text{AF}$.

2.2 File imputed_both_sexes.tsv

At lines 1368 of the already mentioned page with the collection of Neale’s lab metadata ([here](#)), we find the genetic data for the group of patients of both sexes with the phenotype 20002_1482 (Non-cancer illness code, self-reported: chronic fatigue syndrome). The original name of the file is 20002_1482.gwas.imputed_v3.both_sexes.tsv.bgz. In what follows it will simply be referred to by the name imputed_both_sexes.tsv.

Figure 1. Flowchart for the acquisition of the columns of variants.tsv. Each numerical column is then stored in a csv file; each column of strings is stored in three csv files.

Note also that a description of the meaning of the labels of the column of this file is included in the already mentioned README, but I have collected them in Table 2 with only minor changes, to enhance clarity.

variant	Variant identifier in the form "chr:pos:ref:alt", where "ref" is aligned to the forward strand of GRCh37 and "alt" is the effect allele (use this to join with variant annotation file).
minor_allele	The minor allele (alt allele is not always minor).
minor_AF	Frequency of the minor allele in the n_complete_samples defined for this phenotype.
expected_case_minor_AC	(Optional) For case/control phenotypes, calculated as $(2 * \text{minor_AF} * \text{n_cases})$.
expected_min_category_minor_AC	(Optional) For categorical phenotypes with less than 5 categories, calculated as $(2 * \text{minor_AF} * \text{number of samples in smallest category})$.
low_confidence_variant	Flag indicating low confidence results based on the following heuristics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Case/control phenotypes: $\text{expected_case_minor_AC} < 25$ or $\text{minor_AF} < 0.001$. - Categorical phenotypes with less than 5 categories: $\text{expected_min_category_minor_AC} < 25$ or $\text{minor_AF} < 0.001$. - Quantitative phenotypes: $\text{minor_AF} < 0.001$.
n_complete_samples	Number of samples defined for this phenotype and sex (cases + controls).
AC	Allele count of alt allele calculated on dosages within n_complete_samples.
ytx	Alt allele count in cases.
beta	Estimated effect size of alt allele.
se	Estimated standard error of beta.
tstat	t-statistic of beta estimate ($= \text{beta}/\text{se}$).
pval	p-value of beta significance test.

Table 5. Labels of each column of 20002_1482.gwas.imputed_v3.both_sexes.tsv.bgz, and their meanings.

2.2.1 Alternative allele, reference allele, and minor allele

As you can see, several labels of this file have the same name as some of the labels already seen in variants.tsv. But while the label variant indicates the same object in both cases, the others do not. In particular, AC is the alternative allele³ count in n_complete_samples, which is the total size (cases plus controls) for the phenotype considered. This number can be retrieved from the file [phenotypes.both_sexes.tsv](#) along with the values n_cases, n_controls. I report these values in Table 6, not only for both sexes but also for females and males.

Note that by adding the first two columns of Table 6 cell by cell, you get the third one; by adding the first two lines you get the third one. Then, in this case, we have

³ Note that the alternative allele for any given variant is defined by the reference genome of choice (h19, in this case) so it never changes, no matter the sample or file we are considering.

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad \text{minor_AF} = \begin{cases} \frac{AC}{n_complete_samples} = \frac{AC}{361194} & \text{if } AF \leq 0.5 \\ 1 - \frac{AC}{n_complete_samples} & \text{if } AF > 0.5 \end{cases}$$

	n_cases	n_controls	n_complete_samples
females	1208	192945	194153
males	451	166537	166988
both_sexes	1659	359482	361141

Table 6. Number of cases, controls, and total sample, for phenotype 20002_1482 (chronic fatigue syndrome).

3 Reading variants.tsv and writing it in smaller files

Because of the size of the file variants.tsv, I decided to read each column by a different code and to write it in a different file csv file. The csv files written by these scripts are placed in the folder Genetics\Neale's Lab Meta data\Output. I also excluded chromosome X from the analysis, so only the 13,364,304 autosomal variants were considered, with the hope of coming back later and completing the analysis. Three different approaches were employed for the columns with numeric cells and for those with cells containing strings. The flow chart for this part of the analysis can be found in Figure 1.

3.1 Columns with numeric data

To read a column of variants.tsv with numeric data I used the following syntax

```
array_autosomes = dlmread (file_name, '\t', range);
```

I have then stored the array in a cell array array_autosomes_h with the label at the first position (h stands for heading) and saved it as a csv file with the command

```
cell2csv (file_name, chr_autosomes_h, " ")
```

Note that while dlmread is a core function of Octave, to use the cell2csv command you must call the io package at the beginning of your script. As an example, this is the script that reads column B of variants.tsv and saves it in a csv file.

```
% file name = variants_chr_read
% date of creation = 7/09/2021
% it reads column B of variants.tsv
clear all
close all
pkg load io
%-----
% The array of this code corresponds to column B of variants.tsv, but
% only for the autosomes. This means that it has n = 13364304-1 = 13364303 elements.
%-----
n = 13364304 % number of lines including the headers
```

```

strn = num2str(n);
file_name = "variants.tsv"
range = strcat("B2:B",strn);
chr_autosomes = dlmread (file_name, '\t', range);
%-----
% writing the column as a csv file and adding the header
%-----
chr_autosomes_h = cell(n,1);
chr_autosomes_h {1,1} = 'chr';
for i=1:n-1
    chr_autosomes_h {i+1,1} = chr_autosomes(i);
endfor
file_name = 'variants_chr_autosomes.csv'
cell2csv (file_name, chr_autosomes_h, " ")

```

What follows is the list of the scripts that have this same structure, with the description of what they read and what they write.

variants_chr_read	It reads column B of variants.tsv in range B2:B13364304 (only autosomes) and it writes variants_chr_autosomes.csv
variants_pos_read	It reads column C of variants.tsv in range C2:C13364304 (only autosomes) and it writes variants_pos_autosomes.csv
variants_min_AF_read	It reads column O of variants.tsv in range O2:O13364304 (only autosomes) and it writes variants_min_AF_autosomes.csv
variants_p_hwe_read	It reads column P of variants.tsv in range P2:P13364304 (only autosomes) and it writes variants_p_hwe_autosomes.csv

3.2 Columns with string data

To reduce the size of the cell arrays of strings, file variants.tsv was split into three files: variants_1.tsv, variants_2.tsv, variants_3.tsv. The first two contain 5 million lines, the third one contains the remaining 3,791,468 lines. Note that only variants_1.tsv has the headings of the columns. The split was made by using [Big Text File Splitter](#) by Withdata. I used two different methods for reading and writing columns with string data.

3.2.1 First method

We read each line of variants_1.tsv (each line has 25 columns) with the command textscan (which is a core function of Octave, so no package is needed) and we store it in temp, a cell array 1×25 . Then we transform the cells we need with the function char and we store them in a cell array previously defined. Note that if we do not use char, the cell array we end with would be a cell array of cells, instead of a cell array of strings, and it would not be written as csv file in the next section. As an example, this is the script that reads column D of variants_1.tsv, variants_2.tsv, variants_3.tsv and then writes its content in three csv files.

```
% file name = variants_ref_read
```

```

% date of creation = 14/09/2021
clear all
close all
pkg load io
%-----
% The arrays of this code correspond to column D of variants.tsv, but only for
% the autosomes.
%-----
n = 13364304           % number of lines we must read, including the headers
n1 = 5000000;         % number of lines of variants_1.tsv
n2 = n1;              % number of lines of variants_2.tsv
n3 = 3364304;         % number of lines read from variants_3.tsv
%-----
% we initialize the cell arrays
%-----
ref_autosomes_h_1 = cell(n1,1);
ref_autosomes_h_2 = cell(n2,1);
ref_autosomes_h_3 = cell(n3,1);
%-----
file_name = "variants_1.tsv"
fid = fopen(file_name);
for i=1:n1
    temp = textscan(fid, '%s %s %s',...
        1, 'EndOfLine', "\r\n", "Delimiter", "\t");
    ref_autosomes_h_1 {i,1} = char(temp {1,4});
endfor
fclose(fid)
%-----
% writing each column as a csv file (headers included)
%-----
file_name = 'variants_ref_autosomes_1.csv'
cell2csv (file_name, ref_autosomes_h_1, " ")
%-----
% we read each line of variants_2.tsv from 1 to n2 (each line has 25 columns)
%-----
file_name = "variants_2.tsv"
fid = fopen(file_name);
for i=1:n2
    temp = textscan(fid, '%s %s %s',...
        1, 'EndOfLine', "\r\n", "Delimiter", "\t");
    ref_autosomes_h_2 {i,1} = char(temp {1,4});
endfor
fclose(fid)
%-----
% writing each column as a csv file (headers included)
%-----
file_name = 'variants_ref_autosomes_2.csv'
cell2csv (file_name, ref_autosomes_h_2, " ")
%-----
% we read each line of variants_3.tsv from 1 to n2 (each line has 25 columns)
%-----
file_name = "variants_3.tsv"
fid = fopen(file_name);
for i=1:n3
    temp = textscan(fid, '%s %s %s',...
        1, 'EndOfLine', "\r\n", "Delimiter", "\t");
    ref_autosomes_h_3 {i,1} = char(temp {1,4});
endfor

```

```

endfor
fclose(fid)
%-----
% writing each column as a csv file (headers included)
%-----
file_name = 'variants_ref_autosomes_3.csv'
cell2csv (file_name, ref_autosomes_h_3, " ")

```

What follows is the list of the scripts that have this same structure, with the description of what they read and what they write.

```

variants_ref_read          It reads column D of variants_1.tsv, variants_2.tsv, variants_3.tsv (only autosomes)
                           and it writes:
                           * variants_ref_autosomes_1.csv
                           * variants_ref_autosomes_2.csv
                           * variants_ref_autosomes_3.csv

```

```

variants_alt_read         It reads column E of variants_1.tsv, variants_2.tsv, variants_3.tsv (only autosomes)
                           and it writes:
                           * variants_alt_autosomes_1.csv
                           * variants_alt_autosomes_2.csv
                           * variants_alt_autosomes_3.csv

```

```

variants_consequence_category_read  It reads column I of variants_1.tsv, variants_2.tsv, variants_3.tsv (only
                                       autosomes) and it writes:
                                       * variants_consequence_category_autosomes_1.csv
                                       * variants_consequence_category_autosomes_2.csv
                                       * variants_consequence_category_autosomes_3.csv

```

3.2.2 Second method

This method is similar to the one used before, but instead of reading one line at a time, the entire column is read and stored as a cell array. The negative aspect of this method is that we read and write all the lines 3791468, instead of only the first 3364304 (of the column we are considering) of variants_3.tsv. As an example, this is the script that reads column F of variants_1.tsv, variants_2.tsv, variants_3.tsv and then writes its content in three csv files.

```

% file name = variants_rsid_read
% date of creation = 28/09/2021
% it reads column F of variants_1.tsv, variants_2.tsv, variants_3.tsv, but only for autosomes
clear all
close all
pkg load io
tic          % we start counting execution time (seconds)
%-----
% The arrays of this code correspond to column F of variants.tsv, but only for
% the autosomes.
%-----
n = 13364304          % number of lines we must read, including the headers

```

```

n1 = 5000000;          % number of lines of variants_1.tsv
n2 = n1;              % number of lines of variants_2.tsv
n3 = 3364304;        % number of lines read from variants_3.tsv
%-----
% reading column 8 of variants_1.tsv
%-----
file_name = "variants_rsid_autosomes_1.tsv"
fid = fopen(file_name);
rsid_autosomes_h_1 = textscan(fid, '%*s %*s %*
s %*s %*
s %*s %*s %*s %*
fclose(fid)
%-----
% writing each column as a csv file (headers included)
%-----
file_name = 'rsid_autosomes_1.csv'
cell2csv (file_name, rsid_autosomes_h_1{1,1}, " ")
%-----
% reading column 8 of variants_2.tsv
%-----
file_name = "variants_2.tsv"
fid = fopen(file_name);
rsid_autosomes_h_2 = textscan(fid, '%*s %*s %*
s %*s %*
s %*s %*s %*s %*
fclose(fid)
%-----
% writing each column as a csv file (headers included)
%-----
file_name = 'variants_rsid_autosomes_2.csv'
cell2csv (file_name, rsid_autosomes_h_2{1,1}, " ")
%-----
% reading column 8 of variants_3.tsv
%-----
file_name = "variants_3.tsv"
fid = fopen(file_name);
rsid_autosomes_h_3 = textscan(fid, '%*s %*s %*
s %*s %*
s %*s %*s %*s %*
fclose(fid)
%-----
% writing each column as a csv file (headers included)
%-----
file_name = 'variants_rsid_autosomes_3.csv'
cell2csv (file_name, rsid_autosomes_h_3{1,1}, " ")
%-----
% writing the execution time
%-----
execution_time = strcat(num2str(toc/3600), " hours")

```

What follows is the list of the scripts that have this same structure, with the description of what they read and what they write.

```

variants_rsid_read      It reads column F of variants_1.tsv, variants_2.tsv, variants_3.tsv (only autosomes)
                        and it writes:
                        * variants_rsid_autosomes_1.csv
                        * variants_rsid_autosomes_2.csv

```

* variants_rsid_autosomes_3.csv

variants_consequence_read It reads column H of variants_1.tsv, variants_2.tsv, variants_3.tsv (only autosomes) and it writes:

* variants_consequence_autosomes_1.csv
* variants_consequence_autosomes_2.csv
* variants_consequence_autosomes_3.csv

variants_minor_allele_read It reads column N of variants_1.tsv, variants_2.tsv, variants_3.tsv (only autosomes) and it writes:

* variants_minor_allele_autosomes_1.csv
* variants_minor_allele_autosomes_2.csv
* variants_minor_allele_autosomes_3.csv

3.2.3 Third method

Each column was read by using the `csv2cell` command and then written as csv file with the `cell2csv` instruction. This was repeated for each one of the three files obtained from splitting. Note that only the first 3364304 lines of `variants_3.tsv` are read because the remaining ones include variants on chromosome X. As an example, this is the script that reads column A of `variants_1.tsv`, `variants_2.tsv`, `variants_3.tsv` and then writes its content in three csv files.

```
% file name = variants_variants_read
% date of creation = 15/09/2021
% it reads column A of variants.tsv
clear all
close all
pkg load io
%-----
% The arrays of this code contains data only for the autosomes
%-----
n = 13364304                    % number of lines we must read, including the headers
num(1) = 5000000;              % number of lines of variants_1.tsv
num(2) = num(1);               % number of lines of variants_2.tsv
num(3) = 3364304;              % number of lines read from variants_3.tsv
%-----
for i=1:3
    m = i
    strm = num2str(m)
    file_name = strcat("variants_",strm,".tsv")
    strn = num2str(num(i))
    range = strcat("A1:A",strn)
    sep = "\t";
    temp = cell(num(i),1);
    temp = csv2cell (file_name,range,sep);
    file_name = strcat("variants_variants_autosomes_",strm,".csv")
    cell2csv (file_name, temp, " ")
endfor
```

What follows is the list of the scripts that have this same structure, with the description of what they read and what they write.

```

variants_variants_read          It reads column A of variants_1.tsv, variants_2.tsv, variants_3.tsv (only autosomes)
                                and it writes:

                                * variants_variants_autosomes_1.csv
                                * variants_variants_autosomes_2.csv
                                * variants_variants_autosomes_3.csv

```

4 Analyzing autosomal variants for both sexes lumped together

4.1 Reading imputed_both_sexes.tsv and writing it in smaller files

The original name of the file is 20002_1482.gwas.imputed_v3.both_sexes.tsv.bgz. In what follows it will simply be referred to by the name imputed_both_sexes.tsv. As in the case of variants.tsv, I have read it column by column and then stored each column in a csv file. I have used one script for reading all the columns with numeric data and another one for reading string data, as described below. A flow chart for this part can be found in Figure 2.

4.1.1 Columns with numeric data

A single script reads all the columns of imputed_both_sexes.tsv which includes numeric data: columns F, G, H, L. It uses the function dlmread (the method described in par. 3.1). The script is:

```

% file name = imputed_both_sexes_num_read
% date of creation = 7/09/2021
% it reads columns F, G, H, L of imputed_both_sexes.tsv
clear all
close all
pkg load io
%-----
% The arrays of this code contains data only for the autosomes
%-----
n = 13364304          % number of lines including the headers
strn = num2str(n);
file_name = "imputed_both_sexes.tsv"
%-----
% reading numeric arrays (columns F, G, H, L)
%-----
range = strcat("F2:F",strn);
n_complete_samples_autosomes_b = dlmread (file_name, '\t', range);
range = strcat("G2:G",strn);
AC_autosomes_b = dlmread (file_name, '\t', range);
range = strcat("H2:H",strn);
ytx_autosomes_b = dlmread (file_name, '\t', range);
range = strcat("L2:L",strn);
pval_autosomes_b = dlmread (file_name, '\t', range);
%-----
% adding the headers and writing each column as a csv file
%-----
% defining the cell arrays
n_complete_samples_autosomes_b_h = cell(n,1);

```

```

AC_autosomes_b_h = cell(n,1);
ytx_autosomes_b_h = cell(n,1);
pval_autosomes_b_h = cell(n,1);
% writing the headers
n_complete_samples_autosomes_b_h {1,1} = 'n_complete_samples';
AC_autosomes_b_h {1,1} = 'AC_autosomes';
ytx_autosomes_b_h {1,1} = 'ytx_autosomes';
pval_autosomes_b_h {1,1} = 'pval_autosomes';
% writing the numeric values of the cell arrays
for i=1:n-1
    n_complete_samples_autosomes_b_h {i+1,1} = n_complete_samples_autosomes_b(i);
    AC_autosomes_b_h {i+1,1} = AC_autosomes_b(i);
    ytx_autosomes_b_h {i+1,1} = ytx_autosomes_b(i);
    pval_autosomes_b_h {i+1,1} = pval_autosomes_b(i);
endfor
% writing the csv files
file_name = 'n_complete_samples_autosomes_b.csv'
cell2csv (file_name, n_complete_samples_autosomes_b_h," ")
file_name = 'AC_autosomes_b.csv'
cell2csv (file_name, AC_autosomes_b_h," ")
file_name = 'ytx_autosomes_b.csv'
cell2csv (file_name, ytx_autosomes_b_h," ")
file_name = 'pval_autosomes_b.csv'
cell2csv (file_name, pval_autosomes_b_h," ")

```

This is a brief description of this script.

imputed_both_sexes_num_read It reads columns F, G, H, L of imputed_both_sexes.tsv and it writes:

```

* n_complete_samples_autosomes_b.csv
* AC_autosomes_b.csv
* ytx_autosomes_b.csv
* pval_autosomes_b.csv

```

4.1.2 Columns with string data

A single script reads all the columns of `imputed_both_sexes.tsv` which includes string data: columns A, B, E. It uses the method described in par. 3.2.3. In this case, as in the case of `variants.tsv`, we have split `imputed_both_sexes.tsv` into three files and we have written each column in three different files. The script is:

```

% file name = imputed_both_sexes_str_read
% date of creation = 15/09/2021
% it reads column A of imputed_both_sexes.tsv
clear all
close all
pkg load io
%-----
% The arrays of this code contains data only for the autosomes
n = 13364304        % number of lines we must read, including the headers
num(1) = 5000000;    % number of lines of imputed_both_sexes_1.tsv
num(2) = num(1);    % number of lines of imputed_both_sexes_2.tsv

```

```

num(3) = 3364304; % number of lines read from imputed_both_sexes_3.tsv
col{1,1} = "B"; % the first column we read
col{2,1} = "E"; % the second column we read
name{1,1} = "minor_allele"; % name for first output type
name{2,1} = "low_confidence_variant"; % name for second output type
%-----
for j=1:2
for i=1:3
m = i
strm = num2str(m)
file_name = strcat("imputed_both_sexes_",strm,".tsv")
strn = num2str(num(i))
strc = char(col{j,1})
range = strcat(strc,"1:",strc,strn)
sep = "\t";
temp = cell(num(i),1);
temp = csv2cell (file_name,range,sep);
strname = char(name{j,1})
file_name = strcat(strname,"_autosomes_b_",strm,".csv")
cell2csv (file_name, temp," ")
endfor
endfor

```


Figure 2. Flowchart for the acquisition of the columns of imputed_both_sexes.tsv. Each numerical column is then stored in a csv file; each column of strings is stored in three csv files.

This is a brief description of this script.

imputed_both_sexes_str_read

It reads columns B, E of imputed_both_sexes.tsv and it writes:

- * minor_allele_autosomes_b_1.csv
- * minor_allele_autosomes_b_2.csv
- * minor_allele_autosomes_b_3.csv

- * low_confidence_variant_autosomes_b_1.csv

* low_confidence_variant_autosomes_b_2.csv
 * low_confidence_variant_autosomes_b_3.csv

4.2 Writing the output

By combining the content of variants.tsv, imputed_both_sexes.tsv, and line 3 of Table 6 we can find for each variant the frequencies of the two alleles in case and controls, the p value for the comparison between the two groups, and other attributes, like the annotation, the confidence of the result, and more. Let us first have a general overview of the method by which we can find the aforementioned frequencies; we will then see in detail the script that performs the task.

4.2.1 General considerations

We describe here the algorithm for calculating, for each variant, the frequencies of alternative, reference, minor, and major alleles in both cases and controls, by using the content of variants.tsv, imputed_both_sexes.tsv, and line 3 of Table 6. We do that by performing by hand this operation for only one variant, the one in Table 8. Since $AF = 0.505594 > 0.5$, we have that in this case, the alternative allele (A) is the major allele. As a consequence, the reference allele (G) is the minor allele. We can also say that the frequency of the minor allele is $1 - 0.505594 = 0,494406$ and this is because in the present analysis we always assume only two alleles at each position. For this position, we have the values collected in Table 7 where I have not only included those for both sexes (retrieved from imputed_both_sexes.tsv) but also those for females only and males only.

As mentioned, the minor allele G is the reference one, in this case, so if we assumed the same frequency for the minor allele in both cases and control we would have a frequency for G among cases given by

$$\text{minor_AF} \times n_{\text{cases}} \times 2 = 0.494397 \times 1659 \times 2 = 1640.41$$

which is exactly the value of expected_case_minor_AC (rounded at the second decimal digit). The number of alternative alleles in cases is ytx, then the frequency of the alternative and major allele A among cases is given by

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad f_{\text{cases}}(\text{alt}) = \frac{\text{ytx}}{n_{\text{cases}} \times 2} = \frac{1541}{1659 \times 2} = 0,464436$$

Label	Both sexes	Females	Males
minor_AF	0.494397	0.494672	0.494077
expected_case_minor_AC	1640.41	1195.13	445.658
n_complete_samples	361141	194153	166988
AC	365188	196222	168966
ytx	1541	1082	459
pval	$3.95570 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.55504 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0.774073

Table 7. Genetic data for all the sex groups for phenotype 20002_1482 (Non-cancer illness code, self-reported: chronic fatigue syndrome) for the variant we are interested in.

Label	Variant details
variant	13:41353297:G:A
rsid	rs7337312
varid	rs7337312
ref	G
alt	A
consequence	regulatory_region_variant
consequence_category	non_coding
AC	365235
AF ⁴	0.505594
minor_allele	G
minor_AF	0.494406
n_called	361194
n_not_called	0

Table 8. In the third column some of the details for the variant we are interested in, from the variants.tsv file. The column on the center collects the explanations of the labels, from the README file.

Which means that

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad f_{cases}(ref) = 1 - f_{cases}(alt) = 0,535563$$

For the control group we have

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad f_{controls}(alt) = \frac{AC-ytx}{n_{controls} \times 2} = \frac{365188-1541}{359482 \times 2} = 0,505793$$

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad f_{controls}(ref) = 1 - f_{controls}(alt) = 0,494206$$

We can then find the missing allele counts easily from the ones we already know. Hence, the allele count for the reference allele among cases and among controls is given respectively by

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad count_{cases}(ref) = n_{cases} \times 2 - ytx = 1777$$

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad count_{controls}(ref) = n_{controls} \times 2 - (AC - ytx) = 355317$$

where we have considered also that

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad count_{controls}(alt) = AC - ytx = 363647$$

This leads to the values in Table 9. And this is the general algorithm followed for building the output file, starting from variants.tsv and imputed_both_sexes.tsv (plus the numbers n_cases, n_controls

⁴ When AF>0.5 then the alternative allele is the major allele, while the reference allele is the minor allele (see also Table 4).

retrieved from phenotypes.both_sexes.tsv at line 2304 (line 3 of Table 6). This general method is also summarized in Table 10.

Groups	N	Allele A (Alt, Major)		Allele G (Ref, Minor)	
		count	frequency	count	frequency
Cases	1659	1541	0,464436	1777	0,535563
Controls	359482	363647	0,505793	355317	0,494206

Table 9. Frequencies and allele count for both cases and controls (phenotype 20002_1482, both sexes).

Groups	N	Alt Allele		Ref Allele	
		count	frequency	count	frequency
Cases	n_cases	ytx	$\frac{ytx}{n_cases \times 2}$	n_cases × 2 – ytx	$1 - \frac{ytx}{n_cases \times 2}$
Controls	n_controls	AC – ytx	$\frac{AC - ytx}{n_controls \times 2}$	n_controls × 2 – (AC – ytx)	$1 - \frac{AC - ytx}{n_controls \times 2}$

Table 10. The general method for calculating frequencies and allele counts for both cases and controls. Note that n_cases, n_controls are retrieved from phenotypes.both_sexes.tsv at line 2304 and are always the same, while ytx, AC are retrieved from imputed_both_sexes.tsv for each variant.

4.2.2 Description of the script and flowcharts

The script filtered_autosomes_both_sexes.m uses the following csv files, generated from variants.tsv:

```

variants_variants_autosomes_1.csv
variants_variants_autosomes_2.csv
variants_variants_autosomes_3.csv
variants_chr_autosomes.csv
variants_pos_autosomes.csv
variants_rsid_autosomes_1.csv
variants_rsid_autosomes_2.csv
variants_rsid_autosomes_3.csv
variants_minor_allele_autosomes_1.csv
variants_minor_allele_autosomes_2.csv
variants_minor_allele_autosomes_3.csv
variants_min_AF_autosomes.csv
variants_p_hwe_autosomes.csv
variants_consequence_autosomes_1.csv
variants_consequence_autosomes_2.csv
variants_consequence_autosomes_3.csv
variants_consequence_category_autosomes_1.csv
variants_consequence_category_autosomes_2.csv
variants_consequence_category_autosomes_3.csv

```

It uses the following csv files, generated from imputed_both_sexes.tsv:

```
n_complete_samples_autosomes_b.csv
AC_autosomes_b.csv
ytx_autosomes_b.csv
pval_autosomes_b.csv
low_confidence_variant_autosomes_b_1.csv
low_confidence_variant_autosomes_b_2.csv
low_confidence_variant_autosomes_b_3.csv
```

It generates

```
filtered_autosomes_both_sexes_threshold.csv
```

where threshold is a number less than 0.5 that specifies the lowest value admitted for minor AF. This code selects all the autosomal variants included in variants.tsv that verify the following conditions:

```
minor AF >= threshold
consequence category = missense OR pvt OR non_coding
```

Once the variants have been selected, it calculates:

```
alt allele frequency
ref allele frequency
```

in both cases and controls. How the calculation is performed and the meaning of the headers of the output file is summarized in Table 11. The algorithm followed has also been explained in par. 4.2.1

variant	Variant identifier in the form "chr:pos:ref:alt", where "ref" is aligned to the forward strand.
chr	Chromosome of the variant.
pos	Position of the variant in GRCh37 coordinates.
rsid	rsid (not guaranteed to be unique).
minor_allele	Minor allele calculated on n_called from AF ⁵
minor_AF	Minor allele frequency calculated using hardcall genotypes on n_called.
low_confidence_variant	Flag indicating low confidence results based on the following heuristics: - Case/control phenotypes: expected_case_minor_AC < 25 or minor_AF < 0.001. - Categorical phenotypes with less than 5 categories: expected_min_category_minor_AC < 25 or minor_AF < 0.001. - Quantitative phenotypes: minor_AF < 0.001.
1 stands for TRUE, 0 stands for FALSE	
p_hwe	Hardy-Weinberg p-value in n_called.
consequence	Consequence annotated using VEP version 85.

⁵ If AF<0 then Alt = minor allele AND Ref = major allele. Else Alt = major allele AND Ref = minor allele.

consequence_category	Category of VEP-annotated consequence ("ptv", "missense", "synonymous", "non_coding").
pval	p-value of beta significance test in n_cases vs n_controls (see below)
alt_AF_cases	alt AF calculated in n_cases given by $ytx/2*n_cases$
alt_AF_controls	alt AF calculated in n_controls given by $(AC^6-ytx)/2*n_controls$
ref_AF_cases	ref AF calculated in n_cases given by $1-alt_AF_cases$
ref_AF_controls	ref AF calculated in n_controls given by $1-alt_AF_controls$
n_cases	number of cases
n_controls	number of controls
n_called	Number of samples with defined genotype at this variant.

Table 11. Labels of each column of filtered_autosomes_both_sexes_threshold.csv, and their meanings.

We now highlight some sections of the script, using both verbal description and flowcharts. The script can be found in par. 4.2.2.6.

4.2.2.1 Selecting the variants

The script reads variants_minor_AF_autosomes.csv and stores its content (excluded the header) in the array minor_AF. We now select the number of variants such that:

1. minor AF \geq threshold
2. consequence category = missense OR ptv OR non_coding

To do so we introduce three indexes (see also Table 12):

1. k is the number of variants selected plus 1 (it includes the line of the header);
2. h is the line of the variant from 1 to n (n being the total number of lines of variants.tsv);
3. index_h(k) is an array that associates k to h.

The selection of the variants is made more tricky by the fact that the column consequence_category of variants.tsv had to be stored into three files. The flow chart of this section of the script can be seen in Figure 3. Note that minor_AF does not include the header, then minor allele frequency for the variant at line h is minor_AF(h-1). At the end of this section, we have that k is the number of variants selected plus one, and we store this number in lines_h.

⁶ Calculated in n_complete_samples

Figure 3. Flowchart for the selection of the variants that fulfill the requirements on minor allele frequency and consequence_category.

h		k	index_h(k)	num type	string type
1	Header	1	index_h(1) = 1		1
2				1	2
3		2	index_h(2) = 3	2	3
4				3	4
5		3	index_h(3) = 5	4	5
6				5	6
7		4	index_h(4) = 7	6	7
8				7	8
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
n1		k1	index_h(k1) = n1	n1 - 1	n1
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
n2		k2	index_h(k2) = n2	n2 - 1	n2
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
n		lines_h	index_h(lines_h) = n	n - 1	n

Table 12. Meaning of the indexes in `filtered_autosomes_both_sexes.m` assuming that the green cells of the second column are the ones selected according to our filtering requirements. Note that indexes k , h , `index_h` includes the header but the index of numeric arrays does not. Note that $n1 = n2 = 5,000,000$, while $n = 13,364,304$. In this table we have assumed that the variants at lines $n1$, $n2$, n are included after filtering, which is not necessarily true.

4.2.2.2 Reading numeric data

We read the files containing numeric data originally stored in `variants.tsv` and `imputed_both_sexes.tsv`. Those files are

<code>variants_chr_autosomes.csv</code>	<code>n_complete_samples_autosomes_b.csv</code>
<code>variants_pos_autosomes.csv</code>	<code>AC_autosomes_b.csv</code>
<code>variants_p_hwe_autosomes.csv</code>	<code>ytx_autosomes_b.csv</code>
	<code>pval_autosomes_b.csv</code>

Each file is stored in an array, without the header. For each selected position we check that `n_complete_samples_b` is the sum of `n_cases_b` and `n_controls_b`. If this condition is not satisfied, we add one to the variable `error_n_complete_samples_b`. We have already read `variants_min_AF_autosomes.csv` in the section described by par. 4.2.2.1.

4.2.2.3 Reading string data

We read the files containing string data originally stored in `variants.tsv` and `imputed_both_sexes.tsv`. Those files are

Figure 4. Flowchart for the reading of the lines of a string data column.

variants_variants_autosomes_1.csv
 variants_variants_autosomes_2.csv
 variants_variants_autosomes_3.csv
 variants_rsid_autosomes_1.csv
 variants_rsid_autosomes_2.csv
 variants_rsid_autosomes_3.csv
 variants_minor_allele_autosomes_1.csv
 variants_minor_allele_autosomes_2.csv
 variants_minor_allele_autosomes_3.csv
 variants_consequence_autosomes_1.csv
 variants_consequence_autosomes_2.csv
 variants_consequence_autosomes_3.csv
 low_confidence_variant_autosomes_b_1.csv
 low_confidence_variant_autosomes_b_2.csv
 low_confidence_variant_autosomes_b_3.csv

Note that `variants_consequence_category_autosomes_j.csv`, $j = 1, 2, 3$ has already been read in the section of par. 4.2.2.1, so it is not included in this set. For each group of three such files, the scripts follows the algorithm illustrated in Figure 4 for the case of `variants_variants_autosomes_j.csv`, $j = 1, 2, 3$. Note that index h is given by $h = i + (\text{num}(1) * (j-1))$ as it can be easily verified: for $j = 1$ we have $h = 1:\text{num}(1)$; for $j = 2$ we have $h = 1 + \text{num}(1):\text{num}(2) + \text{num}(1)$; for $j = 3$ we have $h = 1 + \text{num}(1)*2:\text{num}(3) + \text{num}(1)*2$, but $\text{num}(1)*2 = \text{num}(2)$ so we have that $h = 1 + \text{num}(2):\text{num}(3) + \text{num}(2)$ which can also be written $h = 1 + \text{num}(2):n$.

4.2.2.4 Calculating allele frequencies for cases and controls

This part has been described in par. 4.2.1. Note that while (see par. 4.2.2.2) we have stored in their integrity (all the 13,364,304 lines) the numeric arrays, we now calculate the frequencies only for the variants at positions `index_h(k-1)`, $k = 2, \dots, \text{lines}_h$. It is important to keep this in mind for the next step.

4.2.2.5 Writing the output

The output is a csv file of 15 columns and `lines_h` lines (including the headers). We store the output in the cell array defined by

```
columns = cell(lines_h,15)
```

We write the first line with the headers. Then we write all the columns employing a loop of `lines_h` cycles ($k = 2:\text{lines}_h$). Note that while the element of the generic column containing string data has index k , the corresponding element for the arrays

```
alt_AF_b_cases, alt_AF_b_controls, ref_AF_b_cases, ref_AF_b_controls
```

has index $k - 1$. Moreover, the corresponding elements of the numeric arrays

```
chr_autosomes, pos_autosomes, minor_AF, p_hwe_autosomes, p_val_b
```

are identified by index `index_h(k) - 1` for the reasons explained in the previous paragraph. The output of the script is

```
filtered_autosomes_both_sexes_THRESHOLD.csv
```

where `THRESHOLD` is the cut-off assumed for minor allele frequency.

4.2.2.6 The script

```
% file name = filtered_autosomes_both_sexes
% date of creation = 09/09/2021
% it generates the file common_missense_ptv_both_sexes.csv by using the package IO
% see https://octave.sourceforge.io/io/ for a description
clear all
close all
pkg load io
tic          % we start counting execution time (seconds)
%-----
```

```

% Data source
%-----
% It uses the following csv files, generated from variants.tsv:
%
% variants_variants_autosomes_1.csv
% variants_variants_autosomes_2.csv
% variants_variants_autosomes_3.csv
% variants_chr_autosomes.csv
% variants_pos_autosomes.csv
% variants_rsid_autosomes_1.csv
% variants_rsid_autosomes_2.csv
% variants_rsid_autosomes_3.csv
% variants_minor_allele_autosomes_1.csv
% variants_minor_allele_autosomes_2.csv
% variants_minor_allele_autosomes_3.csv
% variants_min_AF_autosomes.csv
% variants_p_hwe_autosomes.csv
% variants_consequence_autosomes_1.csv
% variants_consequence_autosomes_2.csv
% variants_consequence_autosomes_3.csv
% variants_consequence_category_autosomes_1.csv
% variants_consequence_category_autosomes_2.csv
% variants_consequence_category_autosomes_3.csv
%
% It uses the following csv files, generated from imputed_both_sexes.tsv:
%
% n_complete_samples_autosomes_b.csv
% AC_autosomes_b.csv
% ytx_autosomes_b.csv
% pval_autosomes_b.csv
% low_confidence_variant_autosomes_b_1.csv
% low_confidence_variant_autosomes_b_2.csv
% low_confidence_variant_autosomes_b_3.csv
%-----
% numbers of cases and controls
%-----
n_cases_f = 1208
n_controls_f = 192945
n_cases_m = 451
n_controls_m = 166537
n_cases_b = n_cases_f + n_cases_m
n_controls_b = n_controls_f + n_controls_m
n_cases = n_cases_b
n_controls = n_controls_b
%-----
% number of lines including header = number of variants + 1
%-----
n = 13364304      % number of lines including the headers
num(1) = 5000000, % number of lines of imputed_both_sexes_1.tsv
num(2) = num(1); % number of lines of imputed_both_sexes_2.tsv
num(3) = 3364304; % number of lines read from imputed_both_sexes_3.tsv
m = 54850;       % number of lines of hg19_genes_autosomes, including the headers
%-----
% threshold for minor allele frequency
%-----
threshold = 0.05
%-----

```

```

% reading and storing data originally coming from variants.csv
%-----
% we select the lines corresponding to variants with minor AF > 0.05 by reading
% file variants_min_AF_autosomes.csv
%-----
% we select the lines corresponding to variants with a consequence category
% missense OR ptv by reading variants_consequence_category_autosomes.csv
%-----
string_2 = 'missense';
string_3 = 'ptv';
string_4 = 'non_coding';
strn = num2str(n);
file_name = "variants_min_AF_autosomes.csv"
range = strcat("A2:A",strn)
minor_AF = dlmread (file_name, '\t', range);
consequence_category_h = cell(n,1);
k = 1; % k will be the number of variants selected + 1
% we store the lines with a variant with minor AF > 0.5
% it is assumed that the first line contains the headers
index_h (k) = 1; % the first line we select is the one with the headers
for j=1:3
    strn = num2str(j)
    file_name = strcat("variants_consequence_category_autosomes_",strn,".csv")
    fid = fopen(file_name);
    for i = 1:num(j)
        temp = textscan(fid, '%s', 1, 'EndOfLine', "\r\n", "Delimiter", "\t");
        string_1 = char(temp {1,1});
        test_1 = strcmp(string_1,string_2); % it is one if the two strings are the same, zero otherwise
        test_2 = strcmp(string_1,string_3); % "
        test_3 = strcmp(string_1,string_4); % "
        test_4 = test_1 + test_2 + test_3; % it is one when the variant is string_1 OR string_2 OR
string_3
        h = i + (num(1)*(j-1)); % the number of the line from 1 to n
        if (h > 1) % we skip the line of the headers
            if ( minor_AF ( h - 1 ) > threshold )
                if (test_4 == 1)
                    k = k + 1;
                    index_h(k) = h;
                    consequence_category_h {k,1} = string_1;
                endif
            endif
        endif
    endfor
endfor
fclose(fid)
clear temp
% we now know that k is 1 + the number of variants with minor AF>0.5 and with a
% consequence category missense OR ptv OR non_coding. We call it lines
lines_h = k
index_h(k+1) = 0; % this is necessary to avoid out of bound error in a following line
%-----
% reading numeric data type
%-----
% we read variants_chr_autosomes.csv
%-----
file_name = "variants_chr_autosomes.csv"
strn = num2str(n);

```

```

range = strcat("A2:A",strn)
chr = dlmread (file_name, '\t', range);
%-----
% we read variants_pos_autosomes.csv
%-----
file_name = "variants_pos_autosomes.csv"
strn = num2str(n);
range = strcat("A2:A",strn)
pos = dlmread (file_name, '\t', range);
%-----
% we read variants_p_hwe_autosomes.csv
%-----
file_name = "variants_p_hwe_autosomes.csv"
strn = num2str(n);
range = strcat("A2:A",strn)
p_hwe = dlmread (file_name, '\t', range);
%-----
% we read pval_autosomes_b.csv
%-----
file_name = "pval_autosomes_b.csv"
strn = num2str(n);
range = strcat("A2:A",strn)
pval = dlmread (file_name, '\t', range);
%-----
% we read AC_autosomes_b.csv
%-----
file_name = "AC_autosomes_b.csv"
strn = num2str(n);
range = strcat("A2:A",strn)
AC = dlmread (file_name, '\t', range);
%-----
% we read n_complete_samples_autosomes_b.csv
%-----
file_name = "n_complete_samples_autosomes_b.csv"
strn = num2str(n);
range = strcat("A2:A",strn)
n_complete_samples = dlmread (file_name, '\t', range);
% we check if n_complete_samples = n_cases + n_controls
error_n_complete_samples = 0;
for i = 2:lines_h
    if ( n_complete_samples(index_h (i)-1) != n_cases + n_controls )
        error_n_complete_samples = error_n_complete_samples + 1;
    endif
endfor
error_n_complete_samples
%-----
% we read ytx_autosomes_b.csv
%-----
file_name = "ytx_autosomes_b.csv"
strn = num2str(n);
range = strcat("A2:A",strn)
ytx = dlmread (file_name, '\t', range);
%-----
% reading string data type
%-----
% we select the lines from variants_variants_autosomes_j.csv, j = 1,2,3 defined by index_h
%-----

```

```

k = 1;
variants_h = cell(lines_h,1);
for j=1:3
    strn = num2str(j);
    file_name = strcat("variants_variants_autosomes_",strn,".csv")
    fid = fopen(file_name);
    h_temp = cell(num(j),1);
    for i=1:num(j)
        h_temp {i,1} = textscan(fid, '%s', 1, 'EndOfLine', "\r\n", "Delimiter", "\t");
        h = i+(num(1)*(j-1));
        if (h == index_h(k))
            variants_h{k,1} = char(h_temp {i,1});
            k = k + 1;
        endif
    endfor
endfor
fclose(fid)
clear h_temp
%-----
% we select the lines from variants_rsid_autosomes_j.csv, j = 1,2,3 defined by index_h
%-----
k = 1;
rsid_h = cell(lines_h,1);
for j=1:3
    strn = num2str(j);
    file_name = strcat("variants_rsid_autosomes_",strn,".csv")
    fid = fopen(file_name);
    h_temp = cell(num(j),1);
    for i=1:num(j)
        h_temp {i,1} = textscan(fid, '%s', 1, 'EndOfLine', "\r\n", "Delimiter", "\t");
        h = i+(num(1)*(j-1));
        if (h == index_h(k))
            rsid_h{k,1} = char(h_temp {i,1});
            k = k + 1;
        endif
    endfor
endfor
fclose(fid)
clear h_temp
%-----
% we select the lines from variants_minor_allele_autosomes_j.csv, j = 1,2,3 defined by index_h
%-----
k = 1;
minor_allele_h = cell(lines_h,1);
for j=1:3
    strn = num2str(j);
    file_name = strcat("variants_minor_allele_autosomes_",strn,".csv")
    fid = fopen(file_name);
    h_temp = cell(num(j),1);
    for i=1:num(j)
        h_temp {i,1} = textscan(fid, '%s', 1, 'EndOfLine', "\r\n", "Delimiter", "\t");
        h = i+(num(1)*(j-1));
        if (h == index_h(k))
            minor_allele_h{k,1} = char(h_temp {i,1});
            k = k + 1;
        endif
    endfor
endfor

```

```

endfor
fclose(fid)
clear h_temp
%-----
% we select the lines from variants_consequence_autosomes_j.csv, j = 1,2,3 defined by index_h
%-----
k = 1;
consequence_h = cell(lines_h,1);
for j=1:3
    strn = num2str(j);
    file_name = strcat("variants_consequence_autosomes_",strn,".csv")
    fid = fopen(file_name);
    h_temp = cell(num(j),1);
    for i=1:num(j)
        h_temp {i,1} = textscan(fid, '%s', 1, 'EndOfLine', "\r\n", "Delimiter", "\t");
        h = i+(num(1)*(j-1));
        if (h == index_h(k))
            consequence_h{k,1} = char(h_temp {i,1});
            k = k + 1;
        endif
    endfor
endfor
fclose(fid)
clear h_temp
%-----
% we select the lines from low_confidence_variant_autosomes_b_j.csv, j = 1,2,3 defined by index_h
%-----
k = 1;
low_confidence_variant = cell(lines_h,1);
for j=1:3
    strn = num2str(j);
    file_name = strcat("low_confidence_variant_autosomes_b_",strn,".csv")
    fid = fopen(file_name);
    h_temp = cell(num(j),1);
    for i=1:num(j)
        h_temp {i,1} = textscan(fid, '%s', 1, 'EndOfLine', "\r\n", "Delimiter", "\t");
        h = i+(num(1)*(j-1));
        if (h == index_h(k))
            low_confidence_variant{k,1} = char(h_temp {i,1});
            k = k + 1;
        endif
    endfor
endfor
fclose(fid)
clear h_temp
%-----
% calculating allele frequencies for cases and controls
%-----
% defining alternate and reference allele frequencies in cases and controls
%-----
for k = 2:lines_h
    alt_AF_cases(k-1) = ytx(index_h (k)-1)/(2*n_cases);
    ref_AF_cases(k-1) = 1 - alt_AF_cases(k-1);
    alt_AF_controls(k-1) = ( AC(index_h (k)-1) - ytx(index_h (k)-1) )/(2*n_controls);
    ref_AF_controls(k-1) = 1 - alt_AF_controls(k-1);
endfor
clear ytx AC

```

```

%-----
% we define the cell array that will contain the whole output of this script,
% including the headers (filtered_autosomes_both_sexes.tsv)
%-----
columns = cell(lines_h,15);
columns{1,1} = "variant";
columns{1,2} = "chr";
columns{1,3} = "pos";
columns{1,4} = "rsid";
columns{1,5} = "minor_allele";
columns{1,6} = "minor_AF";
columns{1,7} = "low_confidence";
columns{1,8} = "p_hwe";
columns{1,9} = "consequence";
columns{1,10} = "consequence_category";
columns{1,11} = "pval";
columns{1,12} = "alt_AF_cases";
columns{1,13} = "alt_AF_controls";
columns{1,14} = "ref_AF_cases";
columns{1,15} = "ref_AF_controls";
%-----
% writing of columns of filtered_autosomes_both_sexes.tsv
%-----
for k = 2:lines_h
    columns{k,1} = char (variants_h {k,1});
    columns{k,2} = chr (index_h (k)-1);
    columns{k,3} = pos (index_h (k)-1);
    columns{k,4} = char (rsid_h {k,1});
    columns{k,5} = char (minor_allele_h {k,1});
    columns{k,6} = minor_AF (index_h (k)-1);
    columns{k,7} = char (low_confidence_variant {k,1});
    columns{k,8} = p_hwe (index_h (k)-1);
    columns{k,9} = char(consequence_h {k,1});
    columns{k,10} = char(consequence_category_h {k,1});
    columns{k,11} = pval (index_h (k)-1);
    columns{k,12} = alt_AF_cases(k-1);
    columns{k,13} = alt_AF_controls(k-1);
    columns{k,14} = ref_AF_cases(k-1);
    columns{k,15} = ref_AF_controls(k-1);
endfor
strn = num2str(threshold)
file_name = strcat('filtered_autosomes_both_sexes_',strn,'.csv');
cell2csv (file_name, columns, " ")
execution_time = strcat(num2str(toc/3600)," hours")

```

4.2.3 Quality tests

Here, we test the output of the script in par. 4.2.2.6 in several ways. If we filter out synonymous variants from the autosomal ones and those with a minor allele frequency below 0.05, we have 6,724,990 variants. The output of the script has 6,724,991, headers included. This is correct.

If we look at the variant of Table 8 in the output of the script, we find that all the results collected in Table 7 and Table 9 are correctly calculated in the output of the script. This variant is at line 10,076,198 of variants.tsv which means that it belong to variants_3.tsv. We must then test a variant

for variants_1.tsv and one for variants_2.tsv. For the former, let us consider the very first variant included in the output:

variant	chr	pos	rsid	minor_allele	minor_AF	low_confidence
1:692794:CA:C	1	692794	1:692794_CA_C	C	0.108677	false

p_hwe	consequence	consequence_category	pval
0.0314373	upstream_gene_variant	non_coding	0.203384

alt_AF_cases	alt_AF_controls	ref_AF_cases	ref_AF_controls
0.103974683544304	0.110667310185211	0.896025316455696	0.889332689814789

We see that the cells that come from variants.tsv are correct. For the frequencies, if we fill the cells of Table 10 with the elements from imputed_both_sexes.csv we have:

Groups	N	Alt Allele		Ref Allele	
		count	frequency	count	frequency
Cases	1659	344.988	0.103975	-	0,896025
Controls	359482	79565.812	0,110667	-	0,889333

As for the variant from variants_2.tsv, let us consider variant 6:1040455:A:C. The output gives for it:

variant	chr	pos	rsid	minor_allele	minor_AF	low_confidence
6:1040455:A:C	6	1040455	rs240667	A	0.217081	false

p_hwe	consequence	consequence_category	pval
0.585203	regulatory_region_variant	non_coding	0.748947

alt_AF_cases	alt_AF_controls	ref_AF_cases	ref_AF_controls
0.785099457504521	0.782951635965083	0.214900542495479	0.217048364034917

We then check in variants_1.tsv the cells originally taken from that file and we see that they are correct. We then build the cells of Table 10 with the elements from imputed_both_sexes.csv:

Groups	N	Alt Allele		Ref Allele	
		count	frequency	count	frequency
Cases	1659	2604,96	0,785099	-	0,214901
Controls	359482	562914,04	0,782952	-	0,217048

I have also checked the p value for these variants. It is the one reported in imputed_both_sexes.csv.

5 Analyzing autosomal variants for one sex at a time

5.1 Females only

5.2 Reading imputed_female.tsv and writing it in smaller files

The files written from variants.tsv remain the same (par. 3), but we must now read imputed_female.tsv (whose original name was 20002_1482.gwas.imputed_v3.female.tsv) instead of imputed_both_sexes.tsv. We split it in

```
imputed_female_1.tsv      (line 1 to 5000000)
imputed_female_2.tsv      (line 5000000 to 10000000)
imputed_female_3.tsv      (remaining lines of imputed_female.tsv)
```

Then we read the numeric columns and the string ones with

```
imputed_female_num_read.m
imputed_female_str_read.m
```

respectively. Those two scripts are identical to the ones described in par. 4.1.1, 4.1.2 and their output is represented by the two groups of files

```
n_complete_samples_autosomes_f.csv
AC_autosomes_f.csv
ytx_autosomes_f.csv
pval_autosomes_f.csv

minor_allele_autosomes_f_1.csv
minor_allele_autosomes_f_2.csv
minor_allele_autosomes_f_3.csv
low_confidence_variant_autosomes_f_1.csv
low_confidence_variant_autosomes_f_2.csv
low_confidence_variant_autosomes_f_3.csv
```

respectively.

...

6 Assigning each variant to its gene (if any)

Once filtered the variants and calculated their frequencies in cases and controls, we are also interested in assigning each one of them to its gene (when possible). To do so we need a list of the starting position and ending position for each human gene, within the reference genome of choice (h19 alias GRCh37). This means that we need a script for writing such a list in a suitable form and one that uses this list for associating each variant of filtered_autosomes_both_sexes_THRESHOLD.csv to its gene (if any).

6.1 Writing a list of human genes and their positions

We start from the zipped file gencode.v19.annotation.gtf ([download](#)), retrieved from the page of genecodegenes.org dedicated to GRCh37 ([link](#)). Once unzipped, I have saved it as xlsx file with the name gencode_v19_annotation_genes_only.xlsx. This file is read by the script in par. 6.1.1, called gene_list_autosomes.m. In particular, it reads It reads columns A (chromosome), D (starting position), E (ending position), I (gene_id), K (gene_type), M (gene_name). It then writes these columns in a new file, called hg19_genes_autosomes.csv. The first lines of this file are collected in Table 13 as an example. Note that the elements of column 5 overlap along the genome. The meanings of the labels in column 5 can be found on [this page](#).

Chr	starting pos	ending pos	gene_id	gene_type	gene_name
1	11869	14412	ENSG00000223972.4	pseudogene	DDX11L1
1	14363	29806	ENSG00000227232.4	pseudogene	WASH7P
1	29554	31109	ENSG00000243485.2	lincRNA	MIR1302-11
1	34554	36081	ENSG00000237613.2	lincRNA	FAM138A
1	52473	54936	ENSG00000268020.2	pseudogene	OR4G4P
1	62948	63887	ENSG00000240361.1	pseudogene	OR4G11P
1	69091	70008	ENSG00000186092.4	protein_coding	OR4F5
1	89295	133566	ENSG00000238009.2	lincRNA	RP11-34P13.7
1	89551	91105	ENSG00000239945.1	lincRNA	RP11-34P13.8
1	131025	134836	ENSG00000233750.3	pseudogene	CICP27

Table 13. First lines of the file hg19_genes_autosomes.csv.

6.1.1 The script

```
% file name = gene_list_autosomes
clear all
close all
pkg load io % see https://octave.sourceforge.io/io/ for a description of pkg
tic % start counting execution time (seconds)
%-----
n = 54849 % lines of gencode_v19_annotation_genes_only.xlsx for autosomes
strn = num2str(n); % conversion to string of the number of lines
file_name = 'gencode_v19_annotation_genes_only.xlsx'
sheet = 'genes'
%-----
% It reads column A and tranforms it from chrn to n format, where n is the number
% of the chromosome
%-----
range = strcat('A1:A',strn)
```

```

[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
temp = text;          % temp is a cell array containing column A1:An
% We convert each cell to string from position 4
% then we transform the string to a number and store it in chr
for i = 1:n
    chr (i) = str2num(substr(char(temp(i)),4));
endfor
%-----
% It reads columns D (starting position), E (ending position)
%-----
range = strcat('D1:D',strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
s_pos = num;
range = strcat('E1:E',strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
e_pos = num;
%-----
% It reads I (gene_id)
%-----
range = strcat('I1:I',strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
temp = text;
gene_id = cell (n,1);
for i = 1:n
    gene_id (i) = substr(char(temp(i)),10);    % this does not include: gene_id "
    tok = strtok (char(gene_id (i)), "");    % we remove the second "
    gene_id (i) = tok;
endfor
%
execution_time = strcat(num2str(toc/60)," minutes")    % execution time
%-----
% It reads K (gene_type)
%-----
range = strcat('K1:K',strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
temp = text;
gene_type = cell (n,1);
for i = 1:n
    gene_type (i) = substr(char(temp(i)),12);    % this does not include: gene_id "
    tok = strtok (char(gene_type (i)), "");    % we remove the second "
    gene_type (i) = tok;
endfor
%-----
% It reads M (gene_name)
%-----
range = strcat('M1:M',strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
temp = text;
gene_name = cell (n,1);
for i = 1:n
    gene_name (i) = substr(char(temp(i)),12);    % this does not include: gene_id "
    tok = strtok (char(gene_name (i)), "");    % we remove the second "
    gene_name (i) = tok;
endfor
%-----
% we now build for each array a cell array with heading
%-----

```

```

cell_array = cell (n+1,6);
cell_array {1,1} = "Chr";
cell_array {1,2} = "starting pos";
cell_array {1,3} = "ending pos";
cell_array {1,4} = "gene_id";
cell_array {1,5} = "gene_type";
cell_array {1,6} = "gene_name";
%-----
for i=1:n
    cell_array {i+1,1} = chr(i);
    cell_array {i+1,2} = s_pos(i);
    cell_array {i+1,3} = e_pos(i);
    cell_array {i+1,4} = char(gene_id(i));
    cell_array {i+1,5} = char(gene_type(i));
    cell_array {i+1,6} = char(gene_name(i));
endfor
%-----
% we now write the output, called hg19_genes_autosomes.tsv
%-----
file_name = 'hg19_genes_autosomes.tsv';
cell2csv (file_name, cell_array, " ")
%-----
execution_time = strcat(num2str(toc/60)," minutes")      % execution time

```

6.2 Associating variants and genes

The script read columns A, B, C, D, E, F of hg19_headers_autosomes.xlsx and also column B, C of filtered_autosomes_both_sexes.tsv and it assigns each variant of the latter to a gene from the former. It handles overlapping genes: if multiple genes are associated with the same variant, they are added on consecutive columns, at the same line, as they are identified. The output file is

filtered_autosomes_SEX_THRESHOLD_genes_over.csv

where SEX is replaced by both_sexes or females or males, and THRESHOLD is the number chosen as a cut-off for minor allele frequency.

6.2.1 Script

```

% file name = genes
% date of creation = 25/09/2021
clear all
close all
pkg load io
tic                % we start counting execution time (seconds)
sex = 'both_sexes'
threshold = '0.05'
%-----
% we read all columns of hg19_headers_autosomes.xlsx
%-----
file_name = "hg19_genes_autosomes.xlsx"
[filetype, sh_names, fformat, nmranges] = xlsinfo (file_name);
strn = char(sh_names(1,2));
strn = substr(strn,5)                % upper limit for range as a string
m = str2num(strn)                    % upper limit for range as a number

```

```

sheet = char(sh_names(1,1));      % name of the sheet
range = strcat("A2:A",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
chr_hg19 = num;
range = strcat("B2:B",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
s_pos_hg19 = num;
range = strcat("C2:C",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
e_pos_hg19 = num;
range = strcat("D2:D",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
gene_id = text;
range = strcat("E2:E",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
gene_type = text;
range = strcat("F2:F",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
gene_name = text;
%-----
% we read columns B, C from common_missense_ptv_autosomes_sex_threshold.xlsx
%-----
file_name = strcat("filtered_autosomes_",sex,"_",threshold,".xlsx")
[filetype, sh_names, fformat, nmranges] = xlsinfo (file_name);
strn = char(sh_names(1,2));
strn = substr(strn,5)           % upper limit for range as a string
lines_h = str2num(strn)        % upper limit for range as a number
sheet = char(sh_names(1,1));   % name of the sheet
range = strcat("B2:B",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
chr_autosomes = num;
range = strcat("C2:C",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
pos_autosomes = num;
%-----
% we assign a gene to each variant in index_h, when possible
%-----
gene_h = cell(lines_h,3);
for i=1:lines_h - 1
    c(i) = 1;
    for j=1:m - 1
        if (and((chr_autosomes(i) == chr_hg19(j)),(pos_autosomes(i)...
            >= s_pos_hg19(j)),(pos_autosomes(i) <= e_pos_hg19(j))))
            gene_h {i+1,c(i)} = char(gene_id {j});
            gene_h {i+1,c(i)+1} = char(gene_type {j});
            gene_h {i+1,c(i)+2} = char(gene_name {j});
            c(i) = c(i) + 3;
        end
    end
endfor
col = max(c) - 3;
%-----
% we define the cell array that will contain the whole output of this script,
% including the headers
%-----
columns = cell(lines_h,col);

```

```

for j=1:3:col
    columns{1,j} = "gene_id";
    columns{1,j+1} = "gene_type";
    columns{1,j+2} = "gene_name";
endfor
%-----
% writing
%-----
for i=1:lines_h-1
    for j=1:3:col
        columns{i+1,j} = char (gene_h {i+1,j});
        columns{i+1,j+1} = char (gene_h {i+1,j+1});
        columns{i+1,j+2} = char (gene_h {i+1,j+2});
    endfor
endfor
strn = num2str(threshold)
file_name = strcat("filtered_autosomes_",sex,"_",threshold,"_genes_over.csv");
cell2csv (file_name, columns," ")
execution_time = strcat(num2str(toc/3600)," hours")

```